

Costa Brava

Operational demo case

Non-official deliverable

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1. Description of the demo site

In the case of the Costa Brava site, a pilot plant integrated with ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules fitted with reverse osmosis (RO) regenerated membranes was installed in December 2019 at the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) of Tossa de Mar. The pilot plant was placed after the sand filter of the tertiary treatment and operated for two years (2020-2021). During this period, this new system's operational conditions and the effluent quality obtained for private gardens' irrigation purposes were evaluated.

2. Motivation for implementing circular economy solutions in the water sector

Costa Brava is a region with high seasonal water demand and frequent water scarcity episodes, which can also cause saltwater intrusion. It is one of the first areas applying water reuse in Europe. In total, 14 full-scale tertiary treatments provide 4 Mm³/year (2016) for agricultural irrigation, environmental uses, non-potable urban uses and, recently, indirect potable reuse.

The Tossa de Mar WWTP works with one-line tertiary treatment with an average flow rate of 7.4 m³/h, ranging from 4.5 m³/h during the winter period (values from 2018) to a maximum of 11 m³/h reached in summer. Mainly during the summer period, both the number of tourists and the wastewater flow rate to be treated increases: thus, a part of the effluent from the secondary treatment is sequentially treated by its tertiary treatment (flocculation/coagulation, pre-chlorination, sand filtration and disinfection process with UV lamps and chlorination).

Nowadays, the effluent from the tertiary system is used for agricultural irrigation and environmental and non-potable water uses. The water excesses flow to the sea. Due to the increase in water demand, especially during summer, improving the final quality of reclaimed water for broadening its application in more restrictive reuses such as private garden irrigation or indirect potable reuse is desired. The NextGen pilot plant pursues this goal.

3. Actions and CS objectives

Table 1. Actions and objectives of the Costa Brava case study.

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target
# 2 Costa Brava (ES) Location: Tossa de Mar	Sub-Task 1.2.2 Integration of recycled membranes in multiquality- multipurpose water reuse	WWTP with a tertiary treatment integrated by a pre-chlorination treatment, a coagulation / flocculation process, a sand filter, and UV lamp treatment. Pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project consists of an ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules that can treat up to 2 m ³ /h of water.	Refurbishment and adaptation of the pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project: ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules are fitted with reverse osmosis (RO) regenerated membranes used as a final treatment of urban effluents in the WWTP of Tossa de Mar to obtain a regenerated water for being used to irrigate private gardens.	TRL 5 → 7	Pilot plant which produces 2 m ³ /h of regenerated water	Regenerated water (2 m ³ /h) for private garden irrigation (RD 1620/2007, Spain) Theoretically: Indirect Potable Reuse by aquifers recharge
		Regenerated effluent from tertiary treatment is nowadays used for public garden irrigation.	Multi-purpose water reclamation and reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Irrigation of private gardens (which requires a higher quality of the effluent compared to the used for public garden irrigation, according to Spanish RD 1620/2007) - Theoretical study of indirect potable water reuse throughout the determination of the emergent pollutants in the regenerated effluent compared with current one. 	TRL 9		

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4. Unique selling points

The unique selling points for the integration of recycled membranes in multi-quality/multi-purpose water reuse are:

- ✓ Tailor made rejection yields (e.g. > 80% of emerging pollutants/priority substances; > 99% of microorganisms; > 95% of salts).
- ✓ Reduction of emerging/priority pollutants that reach aquatic systems.
- ✓ Reuse of a waste (end-of-life RO membranes) that is regenerated (regenerated RO membranes) and can be used in the water cycle as a circular economy concept.
- ✓ Production of reclaimed water with enough quality to be reused. Thus, reduction of the drinking water used for private garden irrigation.

5. Principal characteristics of the technology

1.1. Regenerated end-of-life RO membranes

Ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) are membrane filtration processes whose purpose is to mainly remove suspended solids and organic matter and divalent ions from liquid effluents, respectively. The UF normally works at pressures of 1 – 5 bar (Jafarinejad, 2017) and 5 – 20 bar for NF (Charcosset, 2012). Also, they present zero or low monovalent ions rejection. In general terms, UF is able to efficiently separate colloidal particles, viruses and bacteria (Spivakov & Shkinev, 2005), but has low salt rejection (Calabrò & Basile, 2011). On the other hand, NF not only enables the separation of even smaller organic molecules, but also of inorganic salts. However, it is to note that NF membranes have low rejection of monovalent ions, high rejection of divalent ions and higher permeabilities compared to RO membranes (Wu et al., 2017).

As a function of the oxidation degree, regenerated end-of-life reverse osmosis (RO) membranes can operate as UF and NF modules. In this way, a waste can be reused in the water cycle, increasing their lifetime.

In the NextGen project, the pilot plant, located within a sea container of 20 feet (6.05 m), is fed with water from the sand filter of the tertiary treatment of Tossa de Mar WWTP. The pilot consists of a UF coupled to an NF module, fitted with regenerated RO membranes to produce reclaimed water of Quality 1.1 fixed in the *Real Decreto 1620/2007*. The pilot plant has an estimated production flow rate of 2,2 m³/h. The water produced is disinfected by the online addition of sodium hypochlorite and is stored in a 10 m³ tank. This tank is placed in an easily accessible area, where the water tank truck can pick it up and distribute it to the end-user sites.

The process consists of a 50 µm mesh filter to remove the coarse particulate matter. Next is the UF stage, where one module of a commercial membrane is installed. Finally, the NF stage with regenerated RO membranes occurs. A simplified diagram of the process is given in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows some images of the inside of the plant.

Figure 1. Simplified P&ID of the Nextgen pilot plant.

Figure 2. The general image of the pilot plant equipment

Mesh filter

The function of the mesh filter is to protect the UF process. A 50 μm filter is currently used, but a 10 μm filter can also be installed. An automatic cleaning system is also incorporated, which is activated when a predetermined pressure differential is exceeded. The length of each cleaning step is 30 s, and a feed pressure of 4 bar and a flow rate of 5 m^3/h are required due to pump requirements.

Ultrafiltration

The module consists of a commercial membrane. Back-washes, CEBs and most UF stages are versatile and can be configured and automated using the software developed for the pilot plant. Cleaning-in-Place (CIP) is not automatic and is carried out using the feed tank (500 L). Moreover, there are 3 reagent dispensers for the Chemical Enhanced Backwashes (CEB) which use 3 tanks of 100 L each.

Nanofiltration

The NF process is composed of two sequential modules, a recirculation pump which supplies a crossflow flowrate of 10 m³/h, and 3 tanks (100 L each) for reagent dosage. After each run, the modules are automatically flushed and are fed by the permeate solution (2 x 500 L tanks). The system was configured by carrying out non-automatic CIPs. There also are 3 in line dosing systems (e.g., pH adjustment, anti-scaling reagent dosing, disinfection product) with 3 tanks of 100 L each.

6. Technology implementation requirements

Regenerated end-of-life RO membranes

Mesh filter

A mesh filter must be included at the beginning of the treatment to ensure that coarse solids do not reach the UF module to reduce the number of cleaning cycles and increase the length of the filtration cycles.

Ultrafiltration

UF cleaning should be performed periodically to ensure suitable operation. The following table summarize the most appropriated values of several parameters for the conventional UF.

Table 2. Required operating conditions of the commercial UF membranes.

Parameter	Units	Min	Max	Reference
Transmembrane pressure (TMP)	bar	-	2.1	(DuPont, 2019)
Temperature	°C	1	40	(DuPont, 2019)
pH	upH	2	11	(DuPont, 2019)
Particle size	µm	0.03	0.5	(Spivakov & Shkinev, 2005)

Nanofiltration

Like the UF, NF cleaning should be performed periodically to ensure suitable operation. The following table summarize the most appropriated values of several parameters for the commercial RO membranes. However, these may differ when operating regenerated RO membranes.

Table 3. Required operating conditions of the RO commercial membranes.

Parameter	Units	Min	Max	Reference
Turbidity	NTU	>1	>1	Nextgen D1.2
Pressure	atm	5	50	(DuPont, 2020)
Temperature	°C	1	45	Nextgen D1.2
pH	-	2	11	Nextgen D1.2
SDI	-		5	(DuPont, 2020)
MFI0.45	-		4	(DuPont, 2020)
Oil and grease	mg/L		0.1	(DuPont, 2020)
TOC	mg/L		3	(DuPont, 2020)
COD	mg/L		10	(DuPont, 2020)

Parameter	Units	Min	Max	Reference
AOC	µg/L Ac-C		10	(DuPont, 2020)
BFR	pg/cm ² ATP		5	(DuPont, 2020)
Free chlorine	mg/L		0.1	(DuPont, 2020)
Ferrous iron	mg/L		4	(DuPont, 2020)
Ferric iron	mg/L		0.005	(DuPont, 2020)
Manganese	mg/L		0.005	(DuPont, 2020)
Aluminium	mg/L		0.005	(DuPont, 2020)

7. Results obtained

1.2. Regenerated end-of-life RO membranes

This section presents the results obtained over a year of the NextGen pilot plant operation. During this time, results of water quality (flow, conductivity, turbidity, pH, etc.), emerging pollutants (endocrine disruptors, medicines, etc.) and household products, among others, were recorded and employed to quantitatively assess the efficiency of the treatment through NF regenerated membranes. The efforts on monitoring compounds added to the common physicochemical parameters have been done regarding the intention to use regenerated water for aquifer recharge in Tossa de Mar in the future.

The emerging compounds have been selected according to the WatchList of 2018 and 2020, the Drinking Water Directive and also other literature publications related to the toxicity and effects to the human health. The list of the emerging compounds has been built and agreed with the Catalan Water Agency (ACA, from the Catalan acronym of Agència Catalana de l'Aigua) and the Health Department of the Catalan Government.

- Water quality parameters

The water quality parameters evaluated during the execution of the Costa Brava pilot plant were total suspended solids (TSS), total organic carbon (TOC), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen (NT), total phosphorus (PT), the concentration of chlorides, phosphates, nitrates, nitrites and ammonium, and the total concentrations of calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium ion. Data was recorded from February 2021 to December 2021.

Figure 3 shows the parameters TSS, TOC, COD and chlorides in separate graphs. For all of them, the primary ordinate axis (left) shows the concentration recorded in mg/L, and the secondary ordinate axis (right) shows the tertiary treatment efficiency (%). Dark blue columns show the concentrate (sand filter effluent), and light blue columns show the permeate (effluent after nanofiltration treatment). The grey dots show the nanofiltration efficiency.

As shown in Figure 3, on the graphs (a), (b) and (c), the tertiary treatment efficiency was always around 80%. In some specific cases, and as shown in Figure 3 on the graph (c), there were decreases in COD removal at specific periods. For instance, from March to August 2021, 5 and 35% efficiencies are observed due to the limit of detection was at 50 mg/L and the efficiencies were estimated considering this limit. On the other hand, in September 2021, the analytical method was modified to quantify the low levels of COD. Since then, there was a significant increase in efficiency in the COD elimination, reaching more than 90% in December 2021. Thus, the latter efficiency removal was concluded to be the real efficiency.

The elimination of TSS (Figure 3, graph (a)) was around 80%. TSS concentrations in the nanofiltration effluent were 2.5 mg/L, satisfying the legislative standards established. TOC elimination was about 75% on average (influent concentrations were 1500 mg/L and after the treatment diminished to 300-400 mg/L).

Figure 3. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of (a) TSS, (b) TOC, (c) COD and (d) chlorides during the pilot operation with regenerated end-of-life RO membranes.

The efficiency of chloride removal was also large (80%), satisfying the legislative standards established. Chloride concentrations at the effluent of the sand filter were between 150 and 350 mg/L: after NF, the concentrations were below 100 mg/L. In September 2021, there was an increase in chlorides (350 mg/L). However, the membrane-based system was able to maintain the efficiency producing low chloride concentration effluent (< 95 mg/L Cl⁻).

Annex 1.A exhibits the water quality results obtained for total N, total P, phosphates, nitrates, nitrites, ammonium ions, calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium parameters.

Sand filter effluent registered total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus concentrations around 20 mg/L and 1.5 to 7 mg/l, respectively. After NF, the concentrations were ~10 mg/L for TN and below 0.2 mg/L for TP, registering between 78% and 95% removal efficiency, respectively.

The phosphate concentrations recorded at the outlet of the sand filter effluent ranged from 4 to 16 mg/L. Nevertheless, the concentrations in the NF effluent were stable (between 0.2 and 1.2 mg/L), displaying a high phosphate removal (90 – 95%).

Like phosphates, TN and TP, the ammonia concentrations at the sand filter effluent fluctuated (from 25 to 80 mg/L). However, the concentration in the effluent of the NextGen system was constant (from 10 to 15 mg/L), obtaining removal efficiencies ranging from 75 to 80% of NH_4^+ . In addition, NF membrane (i.e. RO regenerated membranes) exhibited an average removal efficiency of 50% for nitrates and nitrites, being higher in some cases for nitrates (80 – 90%) compared to nitrites (50 – 65%).

Sand filter effluent had calcium and magnesium ion concentrations of 70 mg/L and 25 mg/L, respectively. The results showed that the removal efficiency of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} was independent of their concentrations at the inlet of the NF since there was registered an elimination efficiency of almost 100% in all cases.

An irregularity in the sand filter effluent was registered in June for K^+ , jumping from 20 mg/L to 190 mg/L. However, the tertiary treatment efficiency with regenerated NF membranes was stable, eliminating 80% of the K^+ on average.

The removal efficiency of Na^+ remains stable over time (approximately 80%) regardless of the quality at the inlet of the tertiary system (120 mg/L Na^+). The Na^+ concentrations at the outlet of the NF were stable, around 50 mg/L, reaching removal efficiencies between 75 and 80%. Figure 4 displays the electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (considered as salt concentration) at the NF inlet and outlet throughout 2021. The system exhibited a stable conductivity elimination efficiency (between 70 and 80%).

Figure 4. Electrical conductivity of the concentrate and permeate and the % rejection.

- Endocrine disruptors

Twenty-one endocrine disruptors present in the sand filter effluent and the NF permeate were been analysed, including progesterone, testosterone, bisphenol A and estrones E1, E2 and E3. The analyses were performed every 4 months (March, July, and November 2021). The results obtained in March are presented in this section (See Figure 5), whereas the results from July and November are provided in Annex 1.B.

Figure 5. Endocrine disruptors detected at the outlet of the sand filter and its removal efficiency in March 2021.

All analyses always detected six endocrine disruptors (methylparaben, ethylparaben, propylparaben, caffeine and tris 2-butoxyethyl phosphate (TBEP)). Benzotriazole and tris-chloroisopropyl phosphate (TCPP) were occasionally detected.

In July 2021, the compounds with the highest concentrations were Caffeine (2500 ng/L), Benzotriazole (942.2 ng/L), and TBEP (1447.0 ng/L) and TCPP (2387.1 ng/L).

There is no clear relationship between seasonality and the endocrine disruptors detected. For instance, caffeine displayed high concentrations in both March and July but not November. TCCP registered high concentrations in March, July, and November (2000 – 3000 ng/L). In all analyses, the NextGen system exhibited a removal capacity of approximately 100% (the concentration at the outlet was below the Limit of Detection – LOD).

Some endocrine disruptors, such as ethylparaben or propylparaben, exhibited concentrations between 30 and 180 ng/L, with only a slight removal efficiency (0.5 – 10%).

- **Pharmaceutical compounds**

Eighty-one pharmaceutical compounds were analysed at the sand filter effluent to observe the NF performance of the NextGen system in March, July, and November. Results from March are presented in this section (See Figure 6), whereas results from July and November are given in Annex 1.C.

Figure 6. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the pharmaceutical compounds detected in March 2021

High concentrations of Venlafaxine (4678 ng/L), Hydrochlorothiazide (4451 ng/L) and Valsartan (4019 ng/L) were detected at the sand filter effluent. After the NF, high removal was registered (90 – 95 %). For other compounds such as Erythromycin (495 ng/L), Ibuprofen (421 ng/L), Metoprolol (111 ng/L) or Codeine (81 ng/L), the mentioned influent concentrations were lower, thus a lower removal (i.e., 40 to 60%) was observed.

For compounds such as Ketoprofen (717.8 ng/L), Acetylsalicylic Acid (86 ng/L), Propranolol (139 ng/L) or Meloxicam (59.2 ng/L), the removal was low (around 10%), which could be related to the LOD of some compounds. For instance, Ketoprofen has a LOD of 21.3 ng/L. If the output value registered after NF is close to the LOD, it could interfere, giving lower efficiency values than expected.

Something similar happened with Acetylsalicylic Acid, which has a LOD of 1.2 ng/L. For high concentrations in the NF influent, removal of 85% was observed in July 2021. On the other hand, a low removal (less than 10%) was observed for concentrations close to the LOD (November 2021).

- New pharmaceuticals

In 2021, twelve new pharmaceuticals were added to the analysis. The most frequent detected compounds are Oxypurinol, Gabapentin, Valsartan Acid, and Tramadol (See Figure 7). A high removal efficiency was observed for most of the compounds detected in the NextGen influent (95 – 100%). Results from November are presented in this section, whereas results from March and July are depicted in Annex 1.D.

Figure 7. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the new pharmaceuticals detected in March 2021

Compounds such as Bisoprolol and Lormetazepam had low concentrations (from 20 to 40 ng/L), close to their LOD.

The highest concentrations found were Oxypurinol (3000 to 10000 ng/L), Gabapentin (1000 to 2000 ng/L) and Valsartan Acid (500 to 4500 ng/L). Oxypurinol exhibited a high removal range (from 35 to 80%). The Oxypurinol molecule can easily pass through the regenerated membrane structure, therefore the removal could be related either to the depletion of the membrane or the creation of preferential pathways. On the other hand, Gabapentin and Valsartan Acid registered better removal efficiencies (85 – 95%).

Proper maintenance and periodic cleaning of the membranes unquestionably improve this complex compound removal (recorded removal values around 80% in March 2021).

- Pesticides and herbicides

The The NextGen project analysed eighty-one herbicides and pesticides (results from March are presented in this section, whereas the July and November figures are depicted in Annex 1.E). The compounds detected with higher concentrations were AMPA (3290 ng/L), Diuron (2056 ng/L), Imidacloprid (1146.1 ng/L), Tert-butyl (1058 ng/L), Thiamethoxam (405.8 ng/L), 2,4-D (384 ng/L), MCPA (260 ng/L), Glyphosate (200.0 ng/L), and Mecoprop (70 ng/L).

Although the concentrations in some cases were elevated, the removal efficiency of the NextGen system is high (90 – 95%). Figure 8 shows Diuron is the herbicide with the highest concentration in the sand filter effluent. NextGen's NF system removes 95% of diuron in the outlet. The same is true occurs for AMPA or 2,4-D, NF is effective at eliminating those compounds (98%). The removal of pesticides is crucial, given their toxic nature. Diuron, for instance, is applied to control invasive plants, is considered harmful to humans and is persistent in soil.

Figure 8. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the pesticides and herbicides detected in March 2021.

Chlorpyrifos was detected in all samples. It is a powerful insecticide, usage of which was limited in 2015 and finally banned in 2020. The danger of this pesticide is related to its significant persistence in river and sea environments, which not only prevent the insect fauna proliferation but also affects other families of biota, such as crustaceans and fishes..

- **Household products**

Four household products were detected in 2021: Sucralose, Acesulfame, Paraxanthine and N, N-diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET). Sucralose and Acesulfame are two synthetic calorie-free sugar substitutes (artificial sweeteners). Paraxanthine is a major metabolite of caffeine in humans. Shortly after ingestion, caffeine is metabolized into Paraxanthine. These three compounds were observed in all analyses performed in 2021 (July results are presented in this section, March and November figures are depicted in Annex 1.F). The last compound (DEET) was only detected in the summer (July 2021), as DEET is widely used in household mosquito repellent (See Figure 9).

Figure 9. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the household products detected in March 2021.

The compound with the highest concentrations is Sucralose (up to 7200 ng/L at the sand filter effluent) (See Figure 9 and Annex 1. Nano Filtration efficiency: Household products). In all cases, the NF removal capacity for this compound was 99%. For Acesulfame and Paraxanthine, the results were similar. Although the concentrations of those compounds after the sand filter were low, the removal capacity of the NextGen system was very high, reaching 99% for Acesulfame and DEET in July and November 2021.

- Benzotriazole compounds

Three Benzotriazole compounds were analysed: 5-Chloro-1H-Benzotriazole (CIBTR), 4-Methyl-1H-Benzotriazole (4-TTR) + 1H-Benzotriazole (5-TTR), and 5-6-Dimethyl-1H-Benzotriazole (XTR). 4-TTR + 5-TTR was found at the highest concentrations in all cases. Figure 10 shows the sand filter effluent concentrations recorded during July 2021 (1200 ng/L). The NextGen system did not demonstrate a high removal capacity of this compound (removal efficiency between 10 and 30%) (See also Annex 1.G).

CIBTR and XTR were present at low concentrations after the sand filter (6 to 9 ng/L and 13 to 74 ng/L, respectively). The removal efficiency of the NextGen system is 35 and 80%, respectively. However, we cannot wholly assume these values are correct because they are close to the LOD and therefore possibly related to analytical errors.

Figure 10. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the benzotriazole compounds detected in March 2021.

8. Comparison of baseline situation and Nextgen KPIs

8.1. Regenerated end-of-life RO membranes

At the Tossa de Mar WWTP, tertiary treatment is currently in operation. This tertiary treatment consists of flocculation/coagulation, pre-chlorination, sand filtration and disinfection process with UV lamps and chlorination. The treated water, which meets the limits of RD1620/2007 for public use, is distributed for agricultural irrigation and environmental and non-potable water uses (i.e. public irrigation). As presented in previous sections, the objective of the NextGen pilot plant was to improve the water quality in the effluent using a membrane system to meet the limits of RD1620/2007 for private uses, which are more restrictive than the limits for public purposes. In this section, the baseline scenario is considered, as the water quality at the outlet of the sand filter of the current tertiary treatment at the Tossa de Mar WWTP and the outlet of the membrane-based treatment as the NextGen system.

The plant installed on the Costa Brava demo site within the framework of the NextGen project gave excellent results. It has been proven to remove contaminants of high toxicity, both for the environment and for human health. The increase in water quality during the application of the NF system was noticeable, since all the water quality values at the outlet improved. General KPIs obtained during the NextGen project are presented at Figure 4. It is possible to observe that the water quality at the outlet of the NextGen pilot plant is improved and meets the RD1620/2007 for private uses in terms of turbidity, TSS, E. coli and intestinal nematodes (See also **Error! No s'ha trobat l'origen de la referència.** for further details on the baseline and NextGen systems outlets). Compared to the current tertiary treatment, the NextGen pilot plant was also able to remove about 80% of the emerging compounds (EC). Although their removal is currently not a legislative requirement, the published surface water Watchlist (WL) under the Water Framework Directive (WFD) presents the toxicity levels. Comparing the obtained results with the Watchlist toxicity levels, the effluent concentrations of the monitored EC are below the mentioned levels (see detailed information in previous sections). Regarding physicochemical parameters, it has been observed that NextGen effluent values were lower than the values from the baseline scenario (i.e. outlet of the sand filter). Also, for most of the components, except for ammonium, TN and phosphates, the summer concentrations were significantly higher than winter concentrations. This might be due to the tourist season which triples the population in the town.

Most of the parameter concentrations satisfying the limits not only for private uses but also for indirect potable reuse (i.e. aquifer recharge). However, ammonium concentrations at the outlet of the NextGen system are still above 10 mg/L (limit fixed by Quality 5.1 at the RD1620/2007 for aquifer recharge) which is toxic to organisms and may degrade the water quality of the aquifer (Mohd Kamal et al., 2017). In addition, ammonium under reducing conditions cannot be oxidized to nitrate and it will remain as ammonium or nitrogen gas. Therefore, in order to pursue indirect potable reuse, the secondary treatment must be improved or include a tertiary treatment step on adsorption to increase nitrogen removal from the wastewater.

Surprisingly, average COD concentrations at the effluent of the NextGen system are high, especially in the summer. Until September 2021, the LOD for COD was at 50 mg/L, and the lab method had to be adapted to reach lower levels of COD, which explains the high COD concentrations.

In microbiological terms, no microorganisms were found in the NextGen effluent, and the values comply with the current legislation, i.e. RD 1620/2007. These microbiological parameters have not been monitored at the inlet of the NextGen system since the baseline treatment does not intend to remove microbiological pathogens.

Additionally, it was possible to produce the same flux of treated water (i.e. 13 LMH) with a similar recovery for commercial and regenerated RO membranes (i.e. 70-75%) at a lower transmembrane pressure (TMP). In this case, the TMP for generated RO membranes was between 7 and 8 bar, whereas in the preliminary tests with commercial RO membranes, the TMP was between 11 and 12 bar. Thus, it is translated to less energy consumption (i.e. between 0.9 and 1 kWh/m³ instead of 2 kWh/m³).

The regenerated water, meeting the legislation has been distributed to three private users to irrigate their gardens. Due to the low mineral concentrations of the reclaimed water, some mineralization was needed.

Table 4. General KPIs for baseline scenario and Nextgen system.

Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	NextGen values
Wastewater treatment and reuse	To increase the production of regenerated water for private garden irrigation	Water yield of the system [% of regenerated water produced for private garden irrigation]	0 %	70-80%
	To reduce the salinity of the effluent	Salt rejection yield [% salt removal vs inlet flow]	0 %	75%
	To reduce the content of trace organic compounds (TrOCs) of the regenerated water	Global removal yield for several priority/emergent pollutants [%]	0 %	80 %
	To reduce the TSS and turbidity of the effluent	TSS and turbidity removal yield vs inlet flow to the system [%]	40 %	> 95 %
	To reduce the pathogens content of the effluent	[<i>E.coli</i>] final effluent [CFU/100mL]	1	0
		[Intestinal nematodes] final effluent [egg/10L]	1	≤ 1
[<i>Legionella spp.</i>] final effluent [CFU/100mL]		< 100	< 100	
Energy	To reduce electricity consumption of the Nextgen UF & NF processes compared with conventional ones	Electricity consumption [kWh/m ³ regenerated water]	2 kWh/m ³ (Garcia-lvars et al., 2017)	< 1 kWh/m ³
Materials	Evaluation of the viability of the RO recycled membranes	Flux [l m ⁻² h ⁻¹] related to transmembrane pressure [bar]	13 lm ² h/bar (Garcia-lvars et al., 2017)	13 lm ² h/bar
		Salt rejection [%] compared to a commercial membrane of the same type	> 97% (NF270)	> 75%

Table 5. Monitored KPIs of the baseline scenario and at the outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant.

Parameters (units)	Average			Measures Frequency	Years
	All values	Summer values	Winter values		
Flow rate (m ³ /h)	1.40	1.40	1.40	Daily	2021
COD (mg O ₂ /l)	55.95	10.29	13.00		
pH (upH)	7.47	7.33	7.65		
EC (μS/cm)	1615.64	1627.75	1573.67		
TSS (mg/L)	8.72	9.05	7.63		
Turbidity (NTU)	7.04	7.65	7.04		
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg N/L)	44.60	32.00	71.00		
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg N/L)	2.59	3.35	2.75		
NO ₂ ⁻ (mg N/L)	12.40	19.78	3.00		
Total N (mg N/L)	29.92	25.16	58.50	Monthly	2021
Total P (mg P/L)	8.97	10.70	4.94		
Br ⁻ (mg/L)	0.33	0.30	0.30		
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	237.00	267.75	202.00		
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	8.86	7.45	11.60		
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	61.20	64.75	58.00		
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	15.30	15.75	14.50		
K ⁺ (mg/L)	39.00	65.50	21.00		
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	153.20	151.00	146.00		
E. Coli (CFU/100 mL)					
Legionella spp (CFU/L)					
Intestinal nematodes (egg/10L)				Not measured	
Coliphages (ufp/mL)					
Clostridium perfringens (ufc/100 mL)					
Benzotriazole-H (ng/L)	755.7	621.4	763.70		
Caffeine (ng/L)	3645	2953.3	3722.5	Monthly	2021
AMPA (ng/L)	1889	1943.8	1801.5		
2,4-D (ng/L)	142	111.8	155.3		
Azithromycin (ng/L)	168	79.9	277.2	Monthly	2021

Venlafaxine (ng/L)		332	371	270		
	Parameters (units)	Average			Measures Frequency	Years
		All values	Summer values	Winter values		
NEXTGEN Effluent	Flow rate (m ³ /h)	1.07	1.07	1.07	Daily	2021
	COD (mg O ₂ /l)	28.64	38.75	1.00		
	pH (upH)	7.22	7.23	7.40		
	EC (μS/cm)	395.91	445.00	389.33		
	TSS (mg/L)	2.03	2.11	1.50		
	Turbidity (NTU)	0.33	0.33	0.30		
	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg N/L)	12.84	11.63	17.50		
	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg N/L)	1.83	2.60	1.25		
	NO ₂ ⁻ (mg N/L)	5.45	8.08	1.55		
	Total N (mg N/L)	10.20	9.79	15.00	Monthly	2021
	Total P (mg P/L)	1.90	2.59	0.15		
	Br ⁻ (mg/L)	0.25	0.25	0.20		
	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	64.90	80.50	49.50		
	PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	0.59	0.45	1.15		
	Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	2.40	3.30	1.35		
	Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.74	0.93	0.50		
	K ⁺ (mg/L)	11.03	19.58	4.90		
	Na ⁺ (mg/L)	44.29	48.73	37.50		
	E. Coli (CFU/100 mL)	0	0	0		
	Legionella spp (CFU/L)	0	0	0		
	Intestinal nematodes (egg/10L)	<1	<1	<1	Bimonthly	2021
	Coliphages (ufp/mL)	<1	<1	<1		
	Clostridium perfringens (ufc/100 mL)	0	0	0		
	Benzotriazole-H (ng/L)	544	420.1	636.8		
	Caffeine (ng/L)	333	386.2	312.2	Monthly	2021
	AMPA (ng/L)	78	103.0	65.0		
	2,4-D (ng/L)	19	<10	<10		
	Azithromycin (ng/L)	81	<10.3	81.1	Monthly	2021
Venlafaxine (ng/L)	10	<1.2	9.5			

9. Lessons learned

Required competence	
<p>To operate a membrane-based treatment such the one tested in the CS, specific knowledge about the following systems is required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Membrane filtration process - Membrane cleaning and maintenance - Monitoring and control the plant - SCADA system to operate the plant <p>A basic training is needed to provide the required knowledge to the operator to understand the process as well as to operate it and solve problems encountered during operation. Specific knowledge of the SCADA system is needed to start up and operate the plant on site as well as remotely.</p>	
Maintenance	
<p>Backwashing occur automatically when the TMP is increasing, or the flux is decreasing, as both mean the membrane is clogging. Basic chemical cleanings can also be launched manually once/twice per week. During these cleaning sequences, sodium hypochlorite and chlorohydric acid are used. These cleanings are meant to remove surface deposited material. However, it is recommended to perform a deep cleaning (CIP) every 4-6 months in order to remove more encrusted material and recover initial membrane characteristics and performance.</p> <p>A daily check is performed, which can take 1-2h/day for a trained operator to do a general control during normal operating conditions. Although the CIP is performed automatically, it has to be launched manually. Thus, it requires extra time for performing and supervising the action.</p> <p>Generally, no experts are required for system maintenance. However, external expertise might be needed for major issues regarding electricity, mechanics, or membrane renewal.</p>	
Technological risks	
<p>The main reason for the downtime periods of the membrane-based treatment has been the need for a CIP. This type of downtime was experienced 2-3 times in a year. These downtimes are due to the membrane clogging, producing unstable measurements, an increase of the TMP, and an increase of the automatic cleaning frequency. To minimize the impact of and need for an intensive cleaning, accurate monitoring of the system and performing preventative CIPs when deterioration of membrane performance is determined or after a pre-determined operation time (for example, after 120 or 150 days) is recommended.</p>	

8. Best practice guidelines for operating the technology

Important points to consider during the design and the construction of the plant:

- Installation of a prefilter to remove bigger particles and optimize the operation of UF and regenerated RO membranes (minimizing membrane clogging).
- Need for a high-pressure installation, including appropriate equipment, material, and instrumentation.
- The feed pumps must be properly dimensioned according to the flow and the pressure required by the treatment.
- A chlorination unit is required before the reclaimed water distribution to ensure the minimum free chloride concentration of 0.2 mg/L and no proliferation of microbiological pathogens.
- Water mineralization is needed before the use of the reclaimed water in order to avoid soil deterioration
- A storage tank is required to collect the reclaimed water prior to its distribution.
- The installation needs to comply with the local/state legislation regarding hygiene, security and health safety.

Important aspects to consider during the start-up of the plant:

- Although the valves are controlled automatically, checking that the valves are opened as required is necessary prior to starting-up the plant. Possible to start-up the system as a manual mode to check the operation of the units and its connections.
- Verification of chemical availability and their installation will prevent leakage during operation. Check any leakage in the system.

Crucial parameters for the optimization of the production process:

- For the UF membrane: pressure, temperature, pH, and particle size. The ranges of these parameters are presented in Table 2.
- For the regenerated end-of-life RO membrane (with a pore similar to NF): pressure, temperature, pH, turbidity and silt density index SDI are the key parameters. Also, other physicochemical parameters are suggested (See Table 3).

9. Literature references

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10. Annex 1

A. Nano Filtration efficiency: Water quality parameters

Figure 11. Concentration at inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the water quality parameters. From the left to the right, and from the top to the bottom: (a) total nitrogen; (b) total phosphorous; (c) phosphate; (d) ammonia; (e) nitrates; (f) nitrites; (g) calcium ion; (h) magnesium ion; (i) potassium ion; (j) sodium ion.

B. Nano Filtration efficiency: Endocrine disruptors

Figure 12. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the endocrine disruptors detected in July 2021.

Figure 13. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the endocrine disruptors detected in November 2021.

C. Nano Filtration efficiency: Pharmaceutical compounds

Figure 14. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the pharmaceutical compounds detected in July 2021.

Figure 15. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the pharmaceutical compounds detected in November 2021.

D. Nano Filtration efficiency: New pharmaceuticals

Figure 16. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the new pharmaceuticals detected in March 2021.

Figure 17. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of the new pharmaceuticals detected in July 2021.

E. Nano Filtration efficiency: Pesticides and herbicides

Figure 18. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of pesticides and herbicides detected in July 2021.

Figure 19. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of pesticides and herbicides detected in November 2021.

F. Nano Filtration efficiency: Household products

Figure 20. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of household products detected in July 2021.

Figure 21. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of household products detected in November 2021.

G. Nano Filtration efficiency: Benzotriazole compounds

Figure 22. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of benzotriazole compounds detected in July 2021.

Figure 23. Concentrations at the inlet and outlet of the Nextgen pilot plant and removal efficiencies of benzotriazole compounds detected in November 2021

